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Review

Open government data from a legal perspective: An AI-driven systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

While the applicable legal framework is often identified as one of the key factors in the success or failure of open government data (OGD), the concrete impact of 'OGD law' on actual practices of OGD is often overlooked or hardly addressed in-depth. This contribution therefore aims to disentangle this legal impact based on an AI-driven systematic literature review combining legal and public administration (PA) publications. First, the review shows that OGD law has many faces and cannot be reduced to one single piece of 'OGD legislation'. Instead, OGD law covers a wide range of topics, dealing with access to information, re-use of information, and conflicting interests (e.g. privacy or copyright). Secondly, the article identifies three main dimensions that structure the assessment of the impact of OGD law on OGD practices: topics of OGD law, sources of OGD law, and levels of OGD law. Finally, the review shows that there is no clear and univocal evidence to answer the question of what regulatory constellation is successful in fostering OGD practices and what is not, partly due to a lack of available empirical research. At the same time, the literature reveals some promising avenues for future research on OGD law in action.

1. Introduction

In 2016, both the 250th anniversary of the Swedish Freedom of Information Act (1766) and the 50th anniversary of the United States Freedom of Information Act (1966) were celebrated (Kassen, 2017b; Samahon, 2018). Many countries have followed Sweden and the United States ever since. A legislative wave has even been witnessed in the last two decades with more than eighty countries enacting freedom of information (FOI) legislation (Peled, 2012; Mabillard, Kakpovi, & Cottier, 2018; Berliner, Ingrams, & Piotrowski, 2018;). As a result, more than hundred countries worldwide have some form of FOI legislation now (Shepherd, 2015) and its enactment in other countries is still further promoted (United Nations, 2021).

Apart from this exponential growth in the adoption of FOI legislation, 'modern' FOI legislation goes hand in hand with a 'paradigm shift': where 'passive' disclosure of government information at individual request used to be the cornerstone of traditional FOI legislation, more emphasis is put nowadays on legislation promoting affirmative (proactive) disclosure at the initiative of governments themselves and on Open Government Data (OGD), stressing the need for machine-readable government information to foster its re-use (Moon, 2020; Pozen, 2017). For example, 17 of the 50 states in the United States have laws that formally require executive agencies to make information available in open data formats (NCSL, 2021). In the European Union (EU), the Council of Europe Convention on Access to Official Documents (also known as the Convention of Tromsø), which entered into force in 2020, promotes

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affirmative disclosure explicitly. The new EU Directive on open data and the re-use of public sector information (2019/1024) even recognizes the importance of ‘open data’ explicitly.

All in all, there seems to be a widespread belief across the world that legislation is essential in guaranteeing access to and re-use of government information. This belief is strengthened by several international indexes and projects valuing the existence of such legislation, such as Open Government Partnership, WJP open government index, OECD open government report, and Open Data Charta. At the same time, the actual impact of such legislation on open government data practices is far from clear.

Most of the literature so far discusses a wide variety of drivers and barriers to OGD in practice, such as (the lack of) an administrative culture (Fenster, 2012b; Ingrams, 2017; Khurshid et al., 2020; Shepherd et al., 2019; Wasike, 2020; Worthy, 2013; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014), socio-political influences and economic stimuli (Ingrams, 2017; Khurshid et al., 2020; Krah & Mertens, 2020; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014), informational and technical requirements (Araújo & Reis, 2016; Khurshid et al., 2020; Shepherd et al., 2019) and environmental factors (Shao & Saxena, 2018). Admittedly, several authors in PA literature have also identified the ‘legal framework’ as one of these determinants for OGD practices (Dias, 2020; M. Janssen, Charalabidis, & Zuiderwijk, 2012; Khurshid et al., 2020; Safarov, 2018; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014) and some have even argued that the legal framework is possibly the most important determinant (Shkabatur, 2012; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014). However, as Hossain, Dwivedi, and Rana (2016) already observed, many studies have noted the importance of the legal framework in opening up government data, but have not identified the components of such a legal framework. We refer to ‘OGD law’ to capture all those different components of the legal framework applicable to OGD. The lack of attention for the actual impact of this ‘OGD law’ on practices of OGD can be considered a crucial gap at the crossroads of legal and PA literature, especially since ‘OGD law’ is not a monolith and the impact of the legal framework on OGD practices is not one-directional, as it can act both as a barrier and as a driver to OGD practices.

The aim of this contribution is therefore to review existing literature on ‘OGD law in action’: what is the reported impact of OGD law on practices of OGD? Since the available literature that contains building blocks to answer this question, seems rather scattered and limited, we have undertaken a systematic, AI-driven literature review combining both legal and PA literature on OGD (section 2). After discussing the descriptive statistics of the results of the review (section 3), we take a two-stage approach to answering our research question substantively. First, we unpack the notion of ‘OGD law’ (4.1) and identify three relevant dimensions of OGD law (topics, sources, levels). Next, on the basis thereof, we assess the reported impact of this OGD law on OGD practices (4.2). In our concluding discussion (section 5), we embed our findings by highlighting several contributions to literature and practice and by formulating future research directions.

2. Methodology

Systematic reviews aim to be comprehensive in their coverage of the literature, to pay careful attention to the quality of included evidence, and to take a clear, systematic approach to the synthesis of the data. This study follows the ‘Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses’ (PRISMA) method for conducting systematic literature reviews to ensure transparency and rigor. The PRISMA method involves four phases: identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion (Moher et al., 2009). To accelerate the screening stage, we used AI-based self-learning computer software.

2.1. Identification

First, relevant records in four of the largest academic databases were identified: Scopus, Web of Science, Springer, and HeinOnline. These

databases were chosen because they cover a large and relevant set of social science and legal journals. Since legal definitions are also shaping the conceptual debate in the literature on open government (Tai, 2021), we combined the definitions of OGD by the Open Knowledge Foundation (Open Knowledge Foundation, 2015) and in the EU Open Data Directive as government “data in an open format that can be freely used, re-used and shared by anyone for any purpose” to formulate six search strings.⁴ Five parameters were applied: a) the search string should appear in the title or abstract⁵; b) only academic journal articles were included, to ensure scientific rigor; c) only publications in English were included; d) publications ranging from 2002 to 2020 were included,⁶ and e) all databases were filtered for law and PA topics. The latest revision of the search was done on January 11, 2021.

2.2. Screening

The combined set of records included 2807 references, after removing duplicates. Of these, 209 did not have an abstract available. These 209 articles were screened on relevance separately by reading the introduction. After screening, ten articles were deemed relevant and included in the review. In line with our research question, relevance was defined as dealing with OGD law and its (potential) impact on OGD practices, from either a legal or PA point of view.

Screening 2598 titles and abstracts manually is error-prone and inefficient because of extremely imbalanced data: only a fraction of the screened studies is relevant. To accelerate the systematic screening step, we therefore used ASReview: an open-source AI-based pipeline applying active learning (Van De Schoot et al., 2021).⁷ This enabled us to screen 2598 articles in an efficient and systematic way, overcoming the manual and time-consuming screening of large numbers of studies.

We uploaded a file containing the 2598 records (titles and abstracts) into the software. In the first step, we selected thirty records (fifteen “irrelevant” and fifteen “relevant”) as ‘prior knowledge’ to train the model. These thirty records are the titles and abstracts that we read and categorized manually as relevant or irrelevant for our study, based on the main criterium of relevance described above. While only one record is necessary as prior knowledge, using thirty improves the efficiency of the active learning process. Based on this prior knowledge, a machine learning classifier was trained to predict study relevance from a representation of the record containing text (Van De Schoot et al., 2021).

This led to the second step, the ‘active learning’ cycle. In the active learning cycle, the software presented one new record (title and abstract) to be screened and labeled as “relevant” or “irrelevant” by the user.⁸ The user’s binary label was subsequently used to train a new model, after which a new record was presented to the user. This cycle continued up to a certain user-specified stopping criterion had been reached. The stopping criterion chosen was the top hundred relevant records, which was reached after reviewing 522 records, or approximately 20 % of the entire database. This setup helped to move through a large database much quicker than in the manual process, while, at the

⁴ The search strings were: “open government data + law”; “open government data + regulat*” (regulation, regulatory, regulated, etc.); “open government data + leg*” (legal, legislation, etc.); “open data + freedom of information”; “open data + access to information” and “re-use + public sector information”.

⁵ For the publications for which no abstracts were available (mainly legal publications), the search string should appear in the title.

⁶ In September 2002, the European Commission launched its proposal for a directive on the re-use and commercial exploitation of public sector documents (COM (2002) 207 final).

⁷ Active learning is a type of machine learning in which a model can choose the data points (e.g., records obtained from a systematic search) it would like to learn from, thereby drastically reducing the total number of records that require manual screening.

⁸ Selection of prior knowledge and labeling of records was done by all three authors together to improve validity.

same time, the decision process remained transparent (Van De Schoot et al., 2021). The model seemingly worked well, as the number of relevant records decreased over time during the active learning cycle, meaning that the records were correctly ordered from most to least probable to be relevant. This is depicted in Fig. 1 below, where the green space represents relevant records (decreasing), and the orange space represents irrelevant records (increasing).⁹ Since it is still possible that some potentially relevant articles were not selected by the algorithm, and thus not included in the review, we additionally included articles that were referenced several times in the articles selected by the algorithm, that appeared to be relevant for the purposes of our review based on the titles of those articles. This led to the inclusion of another fourteen articles by snowballing.

2.3. Eligibility assessment and inclusion

The hundred most relevant records identified by the ASReview software, as well as the ten records without an abstract, as well as the fourteen articles identified by snowballing, were assessed for eligibility (a legal or PA article dealing with OGD law and its (potential) impact on OGD practice) by reading the full text. After reading these full texts, another nineteen articles were excluded (six did not have full texts available in English, four were book chapters, and the other nine were simply irrelevant in topic). This left 91 articles from our initial selection. In total, 105 articles were included in this review. Fig. 2 summarizes the data collection procedure.

2.4. Analysis

We first analyzed the 105 articles in our corpus through deductive coding on the basis of three aspects: (1) Research field: Either law or PA, mainly based on the journal, but also checking the content of the article. (2) Method used: Both PA and law have their own distinctive methods. Within law we coded for legal analysis and comparative legal analysis, within PA we coded for empirical and theoretical work, making a distinction between qualitative and quantitative research as well as primary (collecting original empirical material) and secondary (reusing existing empirical material) research. (3) Geographical dispersion: looking at the country or countries under study, if any. An overview of these findings is presented in section 3. We then performed a more inductive open coding on the articles, identifying the various elements of OGD law that were mentioned (such as referring to ‘re-use legislation’ or ‘privacy’), as well as indicators of positive or negative impact mentioned in the articles (this led to codes such as ‘operational detail’ or ‘synchronization’). These codes informed the results in section 4 of the paper.

Fig. 1. Active learning cycle with stopping criterion 100.

⁹ To be sure, it is possible several relevant publications remain in the 2076 unreviewed records. However, as the likelihood of finding additional relevant records decreases, the additional time invested in screening does not outweigh the cost. There are no guidelines to date on appropriate stopping criteria, and as such selecting the 5% most relevant records seemed a balanced choice.

3. Descriptive statistics

3.1. Year of publication

Fig. 3 reveals that the interest in literature for the legal dimension of OGD is quite recent. Most papers are published from 2011 onwards, which is the year that the worldwide Open Government Partnership (OGP) was formally launched (Berliner et al., 2018;). Although legislation relevant to OGD has been enacted before, e.g. the EU Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive in 2003, this legislation has not attracted much attention in legal or PA scholarship and has not been related to the issue of ‘open data’ (Janssen & Dumortier, 2003; Leith & McCullagh, 2004). Furthermore, attention to the legal dimension of OGD seems to be rather constant over the last decade, which is roughly in line with open government research in general (Tai, 2021).

3.2. Research field

Secondly, as our research lies at the intersection of public administration and law, we looked in particular at the distribution of the included articles according to the field. As seen in Fig. 4, the articles are quite equally distributed with 56 articles categorized under public administration and 49 under law. Both perspectives are thus equally represented in this study.

3.3. Methodology used

Fig. 5 shows the different methods used in the articles under review. We discerned seven different methodologies: empirical qualitative research with primary data collected by the researchers ($n = 14$), empirical qualitative research using secondary existing data ($n = 27$), empirical quantitative analysis ($n = 10$), legal analysis ($n = 32$), comparative legal analysis ($n = 4$), systematic literature reviews ($n = 14$), and theoretical literature reviews ($n = 4$). This means that in total there are 49 empirical studies (both qualitative and quantitative combined) and 54 conceptual or theoretical articles. This may seem like an equal distribution, however, since part of the identified empirical research deals with document analysis (rather than interviews, questionnaires, etcetera), it seems safe to conclude that the primary aim in the majority of the articles is not to assess how the legal framework on OGD functions in practice.

3.4. Geographical dispersion

We also looked at the geographical dispersion of the articles under review. Fig. 6 shows that most studies were conducted in Europe ($n = 49$), with the majority situated in the United Kingdom (which can be explained to some extent by the language requirement in the identification process). Compared to Tai (2021) we have more EU-centered publications, which might be due to the search on ‘re-use’ and ‘public sector information’ which is typically European vocabulary. Still, a variety of West-European (multiple in France and the Netherlands), East-European, and North-European countries were included. There were also a handful of studies comparing multiple countries in Europe, usually under the umbrella of overarching EU legislation. The second-largest category were studies done in the Americas ($n = 28$), with a clear dominance of the United States, but also some articles reporting on Canada and Brazil, or comparing across countries over the continent. The next largest category is the group of articles that were compared across continents ($n = 19$). Asian, African and Australian countries were also represented, though in smaller numbers (respectively $n = 6$, $n = 2$, $n = 1$).

3.5. Journals

Finally, we made an overview of the journals in which the articles

Fig. 2. PRISMA flowchart.

Fig. 3. Publication year of included studies.

under review were published. We found a wide variety of both Law and Public Administration journals, along with several niche journals. In total, we had 71 different journals (with 105 articles in total). Most journals only appeared once or twice. This shows that scholarly knowledge regarding the impact of the legal framework on OGD is widely dispersed, highlighting the relevance of this review article to collect key insights across journals and fields. The legal articles were

especially dispersed as there is no dedicated law journal on the topic of government information. Several journals stood out with a higher concentration of relevant articles. These were: Government Information Quarterly (11 articles), Public Performance and Management Review (6 articles), Information Polity (5 articles), and Masaryk University Journal of Law and Technology (5 articles). An overview of journals with at least two publications can be found in Fig. 7.

Count of Field

Number of publications per field

Fig. 4. Research field of included studies.

Count of Methodology

Number of publications per methodology

Fig. 5. Research method of included studies.

4. Thematical review

The substantive question that this article seeks to answer on the basis of a literature review is: what is the reported impact of the legal framework applicable to OGD - here referred to as ‘OGD law’ - on OGD practices? To answer this ‘law in action’ question, we follow a two-stage approach. Section 4.1 will unpack the notion of ‘OGD law’ by distinguishing three relevant dimensions of OGD law. On the basis thereof, section 4.2 will address the impact of these three dimensions on governmental practices of opening up data, based on evidence gathered from the articles under review.

4.1. Unpacking OGD law

4.1.1. Topics of OGD law

Although some publications refer to ‘open government data laws’ or ‘open data legislation’ (Ingrams, 2017; Noveck, 2017; Raines, 2012; Safarov, 2018), these terms are often not further specified. The resulting

uncertainty regarding the meaning of those terms, might be due to the non-legal origins of the concept of ‘open government data’ (Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012b) and its ambiguous relationship to well-established legal concepts such as freedom of information (FOI) and, to a lesser extent, re-use of public sector information (PSI). Nonetheless, even where many open data initiatives do not have an explicit legal basis, they are all regulated by some existing legal framework. This framework is not a single piece of OGD legislation. Instead, there is a patchwork of legislation and other legal sources addressing issues of OGD directly or indirectly. The diversity covered by this collection of OGD laws, can be reduced to three overarching topics that we discerned in the publications under review: access to information, re-use of information, and concurring legal interests.

The first topic of OGD law is *access to information* (ATI): if there is no access to data, they cannot be used or re-used. Although access to information is often equated with freedom of information (FOI) law, the legal literature in our corpus indicates that it is more appropriate to refer to access to information (ATI) law (Berliner et al., 2018; Mabillard et al.,

Fig. 6. Geographic context of included studies.

Fig. 7. Number of Publications per Journal.

2018), as other, sometimes sector-specific legislation on administrative decision-making can be equally important in regulating access to government information as FOI legislation (de Rosnay & Janssen, 2014; van Eechoud, 2016). In addition, the traditional distinction between public access (as with OGD) and private access to government information is increasingly relativized by legal scholars (van Eechoud & Janssen, 2012; K. Janssen, 2011). Nonetheless, most literature still considers FOI legislation as the most important gatekeeper in ensuring access to government information (Berliner et al., 2018). This FOI legislation is often

characterized as legislation dealing with (i) publication at request of (ii) ‘political’ information (rather than ‘raw data’) (iii) to facilitate accountability. Consequently, several notably PA scholars characterize the relationship between FOI and OGD by discontinuity (Berliner et al., 2018; Jaatinen, 2016; Noveck, 2017; Žuffová, 2020): both phenomena are said to differ in underlying motives, timing for disclosure, types of information, and audience (Afful-Dadzie & Afful-Dadzie, 2017; Noveck, 2016; Žuffová, 2020). Others present OGD as some next generation of FOI by stressing that government information (or data) must be made

accessible proactively in a machine-readable way, thereby facilitating its re-use (Moon, 2020; Pozen, 2018). For the moment, this opposite position of considerable overlap or continuity seems to be less dominant in PA literature. Recent literature further signals a shift in FOI legislation, covering not only publication at the request of citizens but also publication at the initiative of governments themselves. Although some legal scholars observe a lack of attention for proactive disclosure (Pozen, 2017; Wagner, 2018), FOI legislation increasingly acknowledges the importance of having access to raw data, as the ‘right to data’ (in a machine-readable format) has already been included in some FOI legislation (K. Janssen, 2012).

The *second* topic of OGD law is re-use of government information or data. Although ‘information’ and ‘data’ are often seen as conceptually distinct (Holwell & Checkland, 1998), OGD law does not always make that distinction, using the terms interchangeably. Thus, for the purpose of this article, we also do not focus on the conceptual differences between the two. Within the European Union, the former Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive is considered as the most important legal document on OGD in the last two decades. At the same time, since this directive only contained a right to re-use at request, but no obligation to disclose proactively, the PSI Directive has often been criticized for insufficiently facilitating access to government information (K. Janssen & Dumortier, 2003). It is apparent that reference to the notion of OGD is completely absent in that directive and the accompanying European legal literature (van Echoud, 2016). An explanation therefore can possibly be found in the origins of the EU PSI Directive, which was already adopted in 2003, long before the concept of OGD became popular (as of 2009). The lack of reference to ‘open data’ is also in line with the idea that OGD is – unlike FOI – often associated with technology rather than regulation (Afful-Dadzie & Afful-Dadzie, 2017; Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012b) and is therefore more often absent in legal publications. Yu and Robinson (2011) signal, however, that new “open government” policies have blurred the binary distinction between the technologies of open data (OGD) and legislation on open government (FOI), especially in the United States. In other jurisdictions than the EU, the distinction between access to and re-use of government information seems to be less strict. For example, in the United States, the Open Government Directive (OGD) of 2009 promotes the public disclosure of high value raw datasets in a machine-readable way, thereby combining access and re-use in one legal instrument (Shkabatur, 2012).

The *third* topic of OGD law is that of concurring interests or conflicting laws. Both ATI and re-use law share underlying objectives of openness and transparency in order to facilitate democratic accountability, citizen participation, and collaboration or economic growth through disclosure of government information. However, apart from the tension between this objective of openness and the administrative burden it entails, there can be other legitimate interests conflicting with the interests of transparency and openness. De Vries (2011) argues that legal questions on (re-use of) public sector information blend at least four areas of law (freedom of information law, ICT law, intellectual property law, and competition law). Sometimes, these concurring or conflicting interests are incorporated in the same piece of legislation, e.g. where FOI legislation refers to data protection regulation or copyright law (Langdon, Yousefi, Relton, & Suderman, 2012). But more often, these different interests are regulated in different pieces of law. The concurring legal frameworks most often identified in our review, are privacy and data protection (Altman, Wood, O'Brien, Vadhan, & Gasser, 2015; Andraško & Mesarčík, 2018; Conroy & Scassa, 2015; Jaatinen, 2016; van Loenen, Kulk, & Ploeger, 2016), copyright (Marcowitz-Bitton, 2015; Okediji, 2016; Oswald, 2012; Saxby, 2008), and national security (Fenster, 2012a; Marcowitz-Bitton, 2015; Pozen, 2017; Pozen, 2018).

4.1.2. Sources of OGD law

For each topic of OGD law identified above, different sources of OGD law can be distinguished. In particular, several publications support the view that OGD law should not be equated with OGD legislation. Instead,

a tri-partition between legislation (statutory law), policy rules (soft law) and case-law seems appropriate.

Most literature under review is concerned with legislation on OGD (either ATI or re-use). Some authors make a clear distinction between legislation and policy, considering legislation as an environmental factor for the adoption of policy (Khurshid et al., 2020; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014). Thus, legislation is an external constraint for authorities developing OGD policies and practices themselves. Others include policy next to formal legislation as sources of law (Styrin, Luna-Reyes, & Harrison, 2017; Wilson & Cong, 2020; Yang, Lo, & Shiang, 2015), which is understandable as far as authorities are bound by these (external) policies. Some literature indicates that there is more variety beyond this binary approach between hard law (legislation) and soft law (policy). Wilson and Cong (2020), for example, provide for a more refined typology of regulatory action, ranging from formal legislation via executive orders to policies and practices.

Legal literature points out another important legal source: case-law. By interpreting and applying legislative provisions on OGD, courts further shape the law on OGD (Figuerola, 2015), as can be observed in Canada (Conroy & Scassa, 2015), the United States (Wagner, 2018), Czech Republic (Antoš (2019) and France (McClean (2017)). In PA literature, this source of OGD law clearly receives less attention than legislation and policies.

4.1.3. Levels of OGD law

It follows already from the description of the different sources of law that the applicable legal framework on OGD is increasingly multi-layered. As a result, OGD law is not restricted to State-centered national law, but also includes binding regulation at an international level (Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012a) and at a decentral or local level (Koningisor, 2020). Upwards, international treaties and other legal instruments (including regulations and directives at the EU level) turn out to be highly relevant for regulating OGD practices. Interestingly, the existence of supranational OGD law varies depending on the OGD topic at stake. Re-use law and conflicting areas of law (e.g. copyright and privacy) are characterized by an impressive body of dedicated international regulation, especially at the EU level, whereas domestic ATI law is often rooted in some constitutional right to government information (Ingrams, 2017) or at most in an (international) human right to freedom of expression (Birkinshaw, 2006). Traditionally, transparency policies and corresponding ATI legislation are studied at the national level. However, OGD law is developed increasingly at the local level as well. In line with this development, recent literature shows an increased orientation downwards, focusing on decentralized rulemaking on OGD by local governments (Dias, 2020; Ingrams, 2017).

Legal literature does not only point out the existence of this multi-level legal framework on OGD, but also the interaction between these different regulatory levels: national legislation implements international treaties or supranational directives (Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012a), whereas national legislation can also instruct local governments how to deal with OGD (Oztoprak and Ruijter (2016).

In Table 1 we provide some examples of OGD law, focusing in particular on OGD legislation, derived from the reviewed literature. To be sure, this overview is not comprehensive but serves as an indication of existing legislation at different regulatory levels and within different regulatory subject-matters.

4.2. Mapping the impact of OGD law

The literature only sporadically discusses the impact of OGD law on OGD practices. In this section we identify and synthesize the impact of OGD law on opening up government data in practice based on the PA and legal literature available. The systematic literature review shows that this impact on OGD can be both positive and negative. In other words, OGD law can function both as a ‘driver’ and as a ‘barrier’, dependent on the particular circumstances. We structure our findings on

Table 1
Examples of legislation related to OGD.

OGD Legislation	Access to information (ATI)	Re-use of information	Concurring interests (e.g. copyright)
International	UN Declaration on human rights	Open Government Declaration (OGP)	Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works
Supranational (Europe)	Council of Europe Convention on access to official documents	EU Open Data Directive	Directive (EU) 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market
Constitutional	National Constitution	*	*
National/ Federal	UK Freedom of information Act 2000	UK Re-use of Public Sector Information Regulations 2015	UK Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988
State level	New York State Freedom of Information Law	Illinois Open Operating Standards Act	*
Local	Pittsburgh Right to Know Law	New York City 'Open data law'	*

* In these cells legislation is usually lacking.

this impact of OGD law on the basis of the three dimensions of OGD law identified in the previous section and add one other dimension on OGD practices 'beyond the law'.

4.2.1. Synchronization between OGD law topics

Where OGD is used as an umbrella term, we discern in the various studies under review three instances of (possible) impact when building on the different topics of OGD law. A first instance is an impact on disclosure of information and providing access to it: OGD law may lead to sharing either more or less information, for instance on government websites or through (denied) responses to individual information requests. (Khurshid et al., 2020; Ma & Lam, 2019). A second instance is an impact on the reusability of data shared. For example, when legislation includes provisions on (re)use of government information, OGD law may encourage public administrations to share data in a more re-usable format (Khayyat & Bannister, 2015; Lee, 2017; Leucci, 2014; van Eeoud, 2016). A final instance of impact is an impact on coordination efforts to share and link data. OGD law might encourage or discourage public administrations to coordinate OGD practices among governments. Legislation can be used to achieve standardization and uniformity among governments (both nationally or internationally) (Saxby & Hill, 2012), thereby facilitating the (re)use of different datasets and linking them together (Pustay, 2016).

This being said, one important element worth reflecting on is the (lack of) synchronization within and between these various topics of OGD law (see section 4.1.1) (Attard, Orlandi, Scerri, & Auer, 2015; Shao & Saxena, 2018). First, issues of synchronization occur in the tension between active and passive disclosure in ATI legislation (Schnell, 2016; Shepherd et al., 2019; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014)). As FOI legislation mainly seems to encourage passive disclosure, making information available on request, and is silent about proactive disclosure, it is up to governments themselves to decide upon active disclosure and to develop suitable policies. Although the proactive release and re-use of readily understandable data could empower citizens and lead to economic gains, governments are hesitant to do so without 'enabling' ATI legislation on proactive disclosure (Koningsor, 2020; Pozen, 2017; Wagner, 2018). Kassen (2017a), however, introduces Estonia as an example where the FOI legislation does contain provisions on proactive disclosure. An interesting finding, however, is that citizens do not necessarily prefer active publication: they are reluctant to gather information by searching and processing datasets, and rather make an FOI request by

sending an e-mail for the desired information (Oztoprak & Ruijter, 2016). Thus, whether legal provisions on proactive disclosure are really helpful in creating a more open government, remains to be seen.

Secondly, a lack of synchronization between the different topics of access (ATI) and re-use is reported more than once. While FOI legislation is often not concerned with issues of re-use, EU re-use legislation has often been criticized for not addressing issues of access, leaving this for Member States to regulate (K. Janssen & Dumortier, 2003). Araújo and Reis (2016) describe how in Brazil transparency (access) and re-use actions are incoherently taken by separate teams that do not keep in contact with each other, which is due to the absence of connecting state legislation. There is also serious concern that the actual reusability of published data is quite low and requires specific skills. In response, national and international case-law currently acknowledges that intermediary bodies such as the media and NGO's play an important role in processing and converting the published data into a more comprehensible format (Balvert & van Maanen, 2019). Gil-Garcia, Gasco-Hernandez, and Pardo (2020) argue that stimulating the (re)use of open data should be an integral part of open data policies, as this is an important factor in creating the intended societal effects of accountability, participation and collaboration.

Finally, a lack of synchronization between OGD law on ATI and re-use and concurring interests in law (most notably privacy and copyright) is observed. Shepherd (2015) stresses that even where FOI legislation establishes a statutory right to access information, it does not in itself guarantee free and unlimited access. Conflicting interests act as a legal barrier that may lead to inaction (Janssen et al., 2012; Wirtz, Piehler, Thomas, & Daiser, 2016). For example, Jaatinen (2016) explores the potential conflict between the right of access to public information and the rights of a copyright holder to control its reuse in cyberspace in the UK. While synchronization of the legal framework, whether or not in the form of a special Open Government Licence (Sappa, Polcak, Myska, & Harasta, 2014; Yoon, Joo, & Kwon, 2019), might be a solution here, literature also makes clear that this tension cannot be entirely removed (Khayyat & Bannister, 2015; Lee, 2017; Leucci, 2014; Okediji, 2016).

A similar statement can be found when considering the conflicting interest of privacy (Janssen and van den Hoven (2015)). Several authors (Langdon et al., 2012; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014; Hardy & Maurushat, 2017; (Andraško & Mesarčík, 2018; Langdon et al., 2012; Shepherd et al., 2019; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014) discuss tensions between FOI legislation and privacy and data protection regulation. Where FOI legislation emphasizes rights of access and transparency, data protection regulation focuses on the risks that come with opening up data and making it available for re-use. Laws regulating public access to government information rely upon a balance between the presumed necessity that the state may keep some information secret and the equally presumed necessity that the public must have access to government information (Fenster, 2012a; Peled, 2012). McClean (2017) describes how in France FOI laws are 'weak' and underdeveloped compared to privacy law, which leads to very few FOI requests in practice. Similar issues are observed in Indonesia by Parung, Hidayanto, Sandhyaduhita, Ulo, and Phusavat (2018), in Tanzania by Shao and Saxena (2018) and in Brazil by Araújo and Reis (2016).

4.2.2. Operational detail of sources of OGD law

Irrespective of the topic of OGD law at issue, it matters *how* this topic is regulated in OGD law. The first important observation here is that OGD law covers more than legislation alone (as discussed in 4.1.2). Wilson and Cong (2020) distinguish six different levels of regulatory action and conclude that cities supported by formal legislation or ordinance are associated with higher dataset provision rates than cities with 'softer' regulatory action, such as recommendations. Styryn et al. (2017) observe differences between countries in the regulation of OGD, comparing the United States, preferring executive action (as illustrated by the Obama administration), with Russia, preferring legislation.

On the other hand, [van Eechoud \(2016\)](#) points out that although a reform of access legislation is one way to ensure that the availability, discoverability and usability of public sector data improves, there are other possibly faster and more effective ways. With reference to the Open Government Partnership, she appreciates ‘softer’ approaches that focus on political commitment to achieve concrete actions, such as national open data action plans or the identification and release of high value datasets. [de Rosnay and Janssen \(2014\)](#) and [Zuiderwijk and Janssen \(2014\)](#) plea for better implementation guidelines next to ‘better’ legislation. This integrated approach has also been emphasized when explaining the success of OGD practices in the UK since 2009 ([Marco-witz-Bitton, 2015](#); [Owen, Cooke, & Matthews, 2013](#); [Saxby & Hill, 2012](#)).

What seems relevant, giving these conflicting signals, is the clarity and detail of OGD legislation. Usually, the lack of specificity in various topics of OGD legislation is presented as a barrier to OGD, especially when it comes to the impact on re-use of data in practice ([Conradie & Choenni, 2014](#); [Langdon et al., 2012](#)). [Ingrams \(2017\)](#) notes that public agencies are more likely to adopt transparency policies when there are clear guidelines offered from the legislature regarding the legal and operational expectations. Equally, [McClellan \(2017\)](#) observes higher FOI requests in countries with clear and detailed legislation, such as the US and the UK, compared to requests in France, where FOI legislation is rather weak and unspecific. A study comparing open data and reuse policies of the UK, the USA, the Netherlands, Kenya and Indonesia ([Nugroho, Zuiderwijk, Janssen, & de Jong, 2015](#)) argues that many national laws lack operational detail and fall short in promoting OGD that is fundamentally reusable. For instance, the absence of a clear and unconditional obligation to publish government data in a machine-readable way is identified as a deficiency in re-use legislation ([Andraško & Mesarčík, 2018](#)). Therefore, some scholars ([Nugroho et al., 2015](#); [Schnell, 2016](#)) suggest including more detailed requirements in legislation, e.g. on minimum data quality and data format. [Worthy \(2010\)](#) points out the importance of having standards of practice enshrined in law because the success of open data initiatives depends on having a common way of organizing, standardizing, and presenting the information in order to make comparison and exchange of information possible in practice. Particular emphasis is put on the need for clear enforcement mechanisms, such as oversight bodies ([Mabillard et al., 2018](#)). In cases of legal uncertainty, public officials will often focus on potential risk, which can lead to tunnel vision on legal compliance and liability (leading to opening up less data in practice), rather than user needs and creating public sector value ([Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014](#); [Cahlíkova & Mabillard, 2020](#); [Shepherd et al. \(2019\)](#)).

On the other hand, the literature is not one-directional, as it also warns that increasing the operational clarity through more detailed OGD legislation comes at a cost ([Khurshid et al., 2020](#)). This is an issue that is faced by the EU, UK and the United States that already have several policies in place ([Nugroho et al., 2015](#)). [Ruijter and Meijer \(2016\)](#) compare the United States rule-based FOI legislation with the Dutch principle-based FOI legislation and show that both regulatory approaches have their respective drawbacks. More detailed legislation can result in easier use. However, these requirements can also be perceived as adding red tape, creating extra administrative burdens, legal barriers and the need to create exceptions to rules. Finally, too detailed legislation on data quality can easily become outdated after a certain period ([Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2011](#); [Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012b](#)). Thus, the question as to the optimal regulatory constellation of OGD law has not yet been answered univocally in the literature.

To be sure, absence of OGD legislation is not necessarily a barrier as such to OGD practices. Admittedly, based on the geographical spread found in the literature, there are important differences in OGD practices between developed and developing countries, which can be explained, at least partially, by the lack of legislation in developing countries ([Nugroho et al., 2015](#)). Thus, several authors add that most developing countries, such as Indonesia or Kenya, are in an earlier stage where there

is awareness about the importance of OGD, but no legislation yet. At the same time, these authors note that there might be soft-law or case-law present that drives opening up data in practice (at least to a small extent) ([Khurshid et al., 2020](#); [Safarov, 2020](#)). Thus, soft law and case law can play an equally important role in promoting OGD. In line with this finding, several authors note that the absence of (formal and informal) rules is especially felt when scaling up OGD, but not when experimenting with OGD ([M. Janssen et al., 2012](#); [Ruijter & Meijer, 2019](#); [Safarov, 2020](#); [Shkabatur, 2012](#)).

4.2.3. Meaningful interaction between levels of OGD law

The third dimension of OGD law, being the international, national or local level of OGD law, also offers valuable insights in the actual functioning of OGD law. Research on legal conditions of transparency policy adoption often focuses on the state and national levels. Acknowledging FOI at the constitutional level is likely to send a powerful signal about the value of transparency to public agencies ([Ingrams, 2017](#)), but this constitutional right needs state-level legislation addressing transparency, such as FOI, as a first step in the institutionalization of transparency policy.

At the same time, legislation on lower levels can also be a strong driving force ([Oztoprak & Ruijter, 2016](#); [Wagner, 2021](#); [Wilson & Cong, 2020](#)). In many countries, local governments have been at the forefront of openness and participation experiences. For example, transparency reforms in the UK date back to the 1960s, in tandem with decentralization policies that devolve more power to the local level ([Oztoprak & Ruijter, 2016](#); [Worthy, John, & Vannoni, 2017](#)). A similar pattern is visible in the United States, where ATI legislation at state level (in so-called ‘public records laws’) or at city level has considerable impact next to the federal FOIA ([Koningsor, 2020](#); [Wilson & Cong, 2020](#)). As such, state laws (as opposed to federal law) have strong potential to steer transparency towards citizens. For example, state governments are seen to turn data requests around more quickly than federal agencies ([Koningsor, 2020](#)). Moreover, city mandates are often tailored in a specific local way, which makes them relevant to local organizational needs and challenges, and especially potent in fostering OGD in practice ([Ingrams, 2017](#)) ([Temiz & Brown, 2017](#)).

The impact of international legislation on OGD practices of national administrative authorities should also not be neglected. Several authors show how EU legislation on re-use has acted as an incentive for the national legislator to improve its legal regime on access ([Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012a](#); [Fenster, 2016](#); [Galetta, 2014](#)). At the same time, [Jaatinen \(2016\)](#) reports a paradoxical effect here in the sense that the EU PSI Directive has affected domestic legal systems with a strong transparency culture more dramatically than those with a secrecy-centric approach: as re-use obligations only apply to information that is already accessible, these obligations hardly affect governments which do not share a lot of information in the first place. This spill-over effect of supranational legislation is not restricted to domestic FOI legislation, but also extends to sector-specific legislation, e.g. food law ([Leone, 2015](#)) and government spending transparency legislation ([Raines, 2012](#)).

A negative effect has also been signaled: the implementation of supranational re-use legislation has sometimes led to a limitation of the access regime in domestic legislation ([Janssen, 2011](#)). Interestingly, there is no direct connection between jurisdictions with a well-established ATI history and the re-use possibilities they offer. Sweden, for example, a FOIA frontrunner, has been considered a slow responder to the PSI directive ([Temiz & Brown, 2017](#)). A similar inconsistency is reported in Brazil, where ‘transparent’ cities are not necessarily most successful in establishing open data portals ([Araújo and Reis \(2016\)](#)). In addition, several authors argue that for successful OGD practices, the mere transposition of international legislation is not sufficient. An integrated approach is needed with the adoption of additional (legal or non-legal) measures, such as codes of conduct and the development of ‘re-use’ licences, to raise awareness, stimulate open re-use policies and

in general to change the culture in the public sector (K. Janssen, 2011; Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2011; Cerrillo-i-Martínez, 2012b). Thus, an impactful implementation of international OGD law requires more than the straightforward ‘copy, paste’ transposition of legal provisions in domestic OGD law.

4.2.4. Beyond OGD law: Between legal text and administrative reality

To conclude this section it is important to add that, while many of the barriers have some roots in the lack of an appropriate legal framework in one way or another, a difference should be drawn between actual and perceived legal barriers. A large part of these barriers will already be eliminated or considerably reduced by increasing the awareness of public bodies and policy makers and educating them on the actual (legal) risks of open data rather than the *perceived* ones. As De Vries (2011) argues, because of the perceived complexity of the applicable legal framework, governments are hesitant to engage in PSI, as they are willing to allow re-use but concerned about the legal consequences and the potential conflicts of laws. Wirtz et al. (2016) find a direct impact of *perceived* legal barriers (e.g. unclarity of legislation, too many legal frameworks) on open government data resistance. This supports the argument that the actual barriers resulting from OGD law should be distinguished more clearly from the perceived ones.

An important note to mention here is the mismatch between the legal and the administrative reality. From a legal perspective, the absence of OGD legislation or the lack of operational detail or synchronization in OGD law can be intentional to provide more discretion to individual public officials or politicians (Shkabatur, 2012). For example, the absence of legislation on OGD licensing can be considered as an implicit invitation to governments to experiment with a variety of approaches combining open data policies and copyright protection (Khayyat & Bannister, 2015; Lee, 2017; Leucci, 2014; Okediji, 2016; Sappa et al., 2014), as licensing of OGD is not only a legal issue, but also one of governmental policy (Khayyat & Bannister, 2015). Zuiderwijk and Janssen (2015) argue that officials, even though some of them appreciate detailed guidance from the legislator, might feel more supported and confident with data release if they could decide themselves on making clear trade-offs for open data publication. This might lead to opening more governmental datasets. At the same time, Wasike (2020) shows that even where legislation leaves administrative discretion to governments, this does not mean that OGD practices will vary heavily across governments, as ‘legacy’ turns out to be important in establishing consistency in FOI practices.

Finally, there is an interesting line of PA literature that links to the unintentional side of OGD law in a positive sense (as a driver). When considering possible responses of governments to FOI requests, a distinction can be drawn between strict compliance (doing as the law asks to varying degrees) and concordance (behaving in ways that move beyond the law and doing more than it asks). Worthy et al. (2017) find that FOI requests can trigger more concordance than compliance. These findings are confirmed by a replicated field experiment in the Netherlands, where the strongest effect of FOI was found on proactive disclosure (concordance), something that governments were not obliged to do according to the Dutch FOIA (Grimmelikhuijsen, John, Meijer, & Worthy, 2019). Thus, interestingly, the absence of a legal framework on affirmative disclosure is not necessarily a barrier to affirmative disclosure, as public officials find incentives for doing more than is required for legal compliance.

5. Discussion

5.1. Key results

This systematic literature review aims to answer the question of the reported impact of OGD law on OGD practices. Our *first* key finding is that a univocal concept of ‘OGD law’ does not exist. Instead, different conceptions of ‘OGD law’ are in use across legal and PA literature, each

emphasizing different aspects of OGD. In order to tackle this obfuscated concept of ‘OGD law’, we propose three relevant dimensions of OGD law. First, there is a need to distinguish different topics of OGD to which the legal framework applies: access to government data, re-use of government data and conflicting interests when opening up government data (4.1.1). Second, there is a need to distinguish between several sources of OGD law, appreciating soft law (policies) and case-law next to legislation (4.1.2). Third, the body of OGD law should be understood as a result of interacting levels of jurisdiction, both international, national and local (4.1.3).

Our *second* key finding is that while existing literature does not answer the million-dollar question of how much, and which type of regulation is necessary and sufficient, it makes clear that the impact of OGD law on OGD practices is not clear cut. For each dimension of OGD law, elements can be identified that can act as drivers, facilitating OGD practices, but also as barriers to OGD practices. As far as the *topics* of OGD law are concerned, the lack of synchronization between different topics of OGD law (e.g. between access and re-use, passive and active disclosure, (re-)use by machines versus citizen-friendly use, and transparency versus privacy) may cause tensions acting as barriers to opening up data in practice, but may also create room for maneuver in OGD practices (4.2.1). The impact of the different *sources* of law is equally ambiguous: where some studies show that ‘hard’ legislation is a strong driver, others argue that soft law can be faster and more effective. Equally, where more detailed legislation might lead to better applicable rules on data quality, it also has clear drawbacks such as adding regulatory burden (4.2.2). Regarding the level of legislation, similar trade-offs occur. Some studies point to the local level as being the strongest driver for providing access, while other authors stress the importance of sending strong signals through national laws. The most contested impact is that of the international level, where some studies argue it can act as a driving force for national or local change, while others argue that it stands in the way of opening up data in practice (4.2.3). This brings us to another important observation: the impact of OGD law on administrative practices is not just a matter of legal drafting, but also of reception of that law by public officials involved in OGD practices taking into account not only the letter but also the spirit of OGD law (4.2.4).

5.2. Contributions to literature and practice

This review has brought together important insights across law and public administration literature. Firstly, we have brought clarity in the obfuscated terminology used in both OGD research and practice. We have teased out important differences in terminology between law and PA scholars, and provided a clear glossary. OGD law covers more than the re-use of ‘open data’ but is also more than freedom of information (FOI) legislation. A lot of the literature on access to government information focuses on FOI, or even equates FOI legislation with OGD legislation (Mabillard et al., 2018), but this is too narrow a conception. Terms are occasionally misused, or at best used differently between law and PA scholars (Yu & Robinson, 2011). The lack of a common vocabulary may be a cause of the limited knowledge exchange between these fields, highlighting the expedience of this review. The recent replacement in the European Union of the PSI Directive by the Open Data Directive in 2019 might be an important milestone in developing that common vocabulary.

Secondly, this review has revealed the complex nature of the interaction between OGD law and OGD practices. In this article we have brought together important tensions and tradeoffs, that were until now scattered across law and PA literature. We show that the studies under review often have contradictory conclusions as to when OGD law acts as a barrier or driver to OGD practices. For instance, some studies suggest more detailed legislation (Ingrams, 2017), while other studies precisely warn against this (Khurshid et al., 2020). Overall, this goes to show that there is no ‘one best way’ to foster OGD in practice, and solutions are highly context specific. This is in line with suggestions from the OGD

ecosystem literature arguing that more attention is needed for the ecosystem in which data is (supposed to be) shared (Dawes, Vidasova, & Parkhimovich, 2016; Harrison, Pardo, & Cook, 2012). Beyond legislation, many other factors affect whether and how information is opened up in practice. We also add to the ecosystem literature by revealing the tensions within OGD law itself. Where ecosystem literature often takes OGD law as a single node in the ecosystem (either in itself or as part of the policy environment), our review provides an account of how various building blocks of OGD law, at various levels of government, with varying levels of detail, can interact to affect OGD practices.

Thirdly, this review also makes a methodological contribution to the literature by using the novel ASReview machine learning tool. The ASReview tool has allowed us to screen thousands of studies through an algorithm, rather than by hand. Where manual screening on imbalanced data, such as studies emerging from search results, is error prone and inefficient, the algorithm allowed for a more effective screening through the active learning cycle (Van De Schoot et al., 2021). Systematic reviewing will increasingly require interaction with machine learning algorithms to deal with the enormous increase of available text. In applying this relatively new systematic reviewing method, we contribute to testing the method's robustness and hope to inspire other scholars to conduct large systematic literature reviews using machine learning methods, rather than continuing to performing these studies manually.

Finally, this review is not only relevant to literature, but also to practice in a two-fold way. On the one hand, given the worldwide tendency to adopt new 'open government legislation', moving away from simply requiring disclosure at request, this review tempers expectations or at least flags issues that need to be considered and monitored during the implementation of OGD legislation, since the mere existence of this legislation will not automatically foster OGD practices. On the other hand, public officials play an important role in weighing tradeoffs and dealing with tensions in OGD law, thereby being crucial actors for the actual impact of OGD law. Yet, these officials often lack key resources and support to perform this role at the best of their abilities, whereas accountability structures are also often lacking to keep this discretionary power in check (Shkabatur, 2012; Zuidervijk & Janssen, 2015). Thus, complementary measures that are in tune with the applicable OGD law, deserve equal attention when aiming at fostering OGD practices.

5.3. Limitations of approach and findings

Admittedly this research faces several limitations. Firstly, we might have overlooked several relevant papers through the ASReview process, although with any systematic literature review there is a risk of missing important papers. We have aimed to compensate for this by also snowballing for articles that were often referenced, to be sure at least some 'key works' are included. Moreover, a wide variety of (both reinforcing and contradictory) findings have been discerned in literature, which might be a sign that no important perspectives have been overlooked. Secondly, only English papers have been included in the selection because of practical reasons. For the purposes of this article, this can be a significant limitation, since in many countries legal texts are not automatically published in English, but only in the domestic language. The same holds for legal articles discussing (the impact of) those domestic legal documents. This may leave this review vulnerable to over-representing Western perspectives or perspectives of English-speaking countries, as the geographic dispersion of articles under review in section 3 confirms. Thirdly, the focus in search terms might have resulted in an overrepresentation of 'hard' OGD law (legislation). Policies have only been included in the review as far as literature has identified these policies as 'soft law' for authorities engaged in OGD practices. Although this approach is in line with the aim of this paper to consider OGD law as an external constraint for governmental action, which is not the case with self-imposed policies that administrative authorities can change themselves, the downside of this approach might have been that other

legal instruments with a similar binding effect (e.g. 'guidelines', etcetera) have been overlooked in the review.

5.4. Conclusion and future research questions

Existing literature in law and PA does not provide a straightforward answer to the impact of OGD law on OGD practices. This is not only due to the multidimensionality of OGD law, which makes it necessary to better disentangle the concept of 'OGD' law and to carefully map the interplay between different topics, sources and levels of OGD law. The lack of a straightforward answer is also the result of the divergent responses to OGD law of authorities involved in OGD practices. Thus, OGD law is presented as a powerful driver for OGD practices in some particular context, while being disqualified as a driver in another context.

Several suggestions for future research therefore remain. Firstly, PA and legal scholars should work together more to disentangle the actual versus the perceived barriers of the legal framework applicable to OGD: where the legal framework is often perceived as complicated and thereby hindering OGD, legal analysis can unveil whether this perception is justified or not. At the same time, legal scholarship should be more aware of the perception of legislation in governmental practice and, in particular, on the 'chilling effects' of legislation that aims to foster OGD but makes governments and individual public officials uncertain how to proceed.

Secondly, future research needs to take a closer look at the tradeoffs in OGD law discussed above. Since empirical research is lagging here, this kind of 'law in action' research should be welcomed, especially beyond existing field experiments dealing with traditional FOI requests because of the rapid transformation of OGD legislation. A promising avenue could be to further develop the notions of 'strong' and 'weak' OGD laws (McClellan, 2017). Careful attention should be paid here to the multi-faced character of OGD, as, for example, a lack of FOI appeals may be used to disqualify FOI legislation but can also be indicative of good legislation in favor of affirmative disclosure making FOI appeals redundant.

Thirdly and finally, the dynamics between the legal framework and other drivers and barriers to OGD deserves (more) careful attention, as the impact of the legal framework seems to go beyond strict legal compliance of OGD initiatives. To be sure, effective transparent and reusable OGD will not be achieved by legislation alone. Effective transparency is likely to remain elusive unless public officials, civil society organizations, and citizens accept it as a fundamental democratic principle and develop the skills and capacities to supply or demand it (Schnell, 2016).

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Shirley Kempeneer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Ali Pirannejad:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Johan Wolswinkel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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